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Biochemical and Hematological Parameters of Blood of Small Cattle When Feeding a New Feed Additive on Fattening

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the physiological and biochemical efficacy of a new feed additive and its use based on laboratory studies. The use of a new feed additive has an effect on protein, carbohydrate and fat metabolism in the body, contributes to an increase in animal weight. The feed additive has a good adsorption and antioxidant effect, reduces the amount of toxic products, participates in the inactivation of free radicals and has a protective effect on cell membranes. It has been investigated that the use of a new feed additive leads to a significant improvement in growth and reduces lipid peroxidation, namely, it reduces the content of malondialdehyde and diene conjugates in the blood, and the most positive effect of these complexes on the protein and carbohydrate metabolism of sheep of both groups during feeding has been established.

Key words: antioxidant, blood, feed additive, metabolism, Sheep

1. Introduction

Animal husbandry is a priority area of development of agriculture in the Republic of Kazakhstan, the most important source of economic growth of the country and improvement of living standards of the population. And one of the strategic tasks of agriculture is to ensure food security of the country, and today it requires diverse, including scientific support. The potential of the domestic agricultural sector is colossal - there are large areas of agricultural land. However, in almost all sectors, low productivity is observed [Tokayev, 2019, 2021, 2021]. In addition, the physiological functions of animals undergo certain changes with age, depend on productivity and other factors [Gomez-Miranda, et al., 2020; Brassard, et al., 2024; Bhati, et al., 2017].

To increase the productivity of farm animals, many biologically active substances are currently used, including various plant extracts [Alem, 2024; Artuso-Ponte, et al., 2020]. In addition to external and internal factors affecting the productivity of farm animals, fatness is of great importance. Feed additives, along with feed, are one of the main factors in improving the quality of animal feed, as well as strengthening their health [Kiczorowska, et al., 2017; Bakhtiyarova, et al., 2025].

Environmental conditions, poor feed quality, high disease levels, low genetic resources and weak market infrastructure are all factors that negatively affect livestock production and its products, including feed shortages, seasonal changes and some natural factors. The intensification of industrial livestock farming leads to excessive functional stress on the animal's body. Metabolic diseases are the main factor in reducing animal productivity and agricultural output [Mohamed, et al., 2024]. In recent years, natural products have gained great importance as growth-promoting products, and can have a positive impact on improving livestock production, minimizing economic losses, and ensuring the safety of products for human consumption [Nastoh, et al., 2024; Demchenko, et al., 2022]. Currently, feeding standards are being developed and implemented based on a deep study of the digestive processes occurring in the body of highly productive animals, which are necessary for the biosynthesis of milk components and improving the quality of the resulting product [Ronald, et al., 2020; Boyko, et al., 2021]. The use of various feed additives, including non-traditional ones, allows us to improve and regulate the composition of feed, as well as improve the metabolism of farm animals and increase the efficiency of their use of products [Caprarulo, et al., 2020].

Feed additives (FA) are intentionally added to the diet of livestock or drinking water to improve feed quality and have a positive effect on animal productivity [Placha, et al., 2022]. The composition of the FA must correspond to the normative data of any diet for feeding farm animals. For enhanced growth of young small cattle (YSC), vitamins and minerals such as calcium, fluorine, phosphorus, and vitamin D are necessary [Alipour, et al., 2019; Nigmatyanov, et al., 2020].

Feed additives are substances added to animal feed to improve the taste of feed and its health, improve the quality of products, increase the rate of its growth, as they have anthelmintic, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory, as well as antioxidant properties and improve microbiological activity, and are aimed at improving the quality of livestock products and animal productivity [Silveira, et al., 2021; Bostami, et al., 2021; Chan, et al., 2018].

Normal vitamin A content is responsible for the normal functioning of the digestive system, prevents miscarriages, improves reproductive function, stimulates the growth of young animals, and prevents obesity [Shastak, et al., 2024; Baker, et al., 1986]. Such as iodine and zinc maintain stable milk yields, reproductive function, and are responsible for the normal functioning of the thyroid gland [Mobashar, et al., 2024; Gelaye, 2024]. Potassium and sodium control the water-salt balance, prevent the occurrence of anemia [Najjar, 2023; Yang, 2023] in case of cardiovascular disorders.

The use of feed additives allows livestock specialists to comprehensively mechanize and automate the processes of preparing and distributing feed. Feed additives are the most effective type of feed that meets the physiological needs of farm animals. According to literary sources, the result of using additives is not only an increase in the body weight of farm animals, but also an increase in their productivity, as well as an increase in the economic efficiency of the country [Singh, 2015; Pandey, et al., 2019].

The use of various fortified feed additives improves the functional activity of digestive processes, stimulates the growth and development of young animals, and affects the quality of meat and dairy products. At this time, the study of patterns of changes in blood parameters during growth, development, and formation of productive qualities of animals is of great practical interest in the agro-industrial sector. Studies of blood circulation, as the internal environment of any organism, anatomically and functionally interconnected with the digestive system of animals, are necessary to identify water-salt, biochemical, and enzymatic processes occurring in the body after the use of various feeds or feed additives, which is necessary to obtain high-quality products. The purpose of the research was to study the dynamics of biochemical and hematological blood parameters of ewes using new feed additives in the diet and to give a physiological and biochemical assessment of their effectiveness.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animal use

All experiments with animals were conducted in strict accordance with the rules developed and approved by the local Ethical Committee of the Institute of Genetics and Physiology, Protocol No. 07-05/158 of October 08, 2024, as well as in accordance with the rules of bioethics approved by the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrates (Strasbourg, 1986) and the guidelines outlined in the European

Union Directive 2010/63/EU of September 22, 2010, "On the protection of animals used for scientific purposes".

2.2. Experimental Layout

The experimental part of the work was carried out on a peasant farm (PF) in Almaty and Zhambyl regions during the winter season. The studies were conducted on 100 ewes of different productivity directions, including PF "Mamed-Khasenov" (Almaty region) - Hampshire breed (50 rams - producers) weighing 64 ± 2.7 kilograms and PF "Razakhun" (Zhambyl region) - Kazakh meat wool (50 rams - producers) weighing 64 ± 2.7 kilograms, we formed 2 groups by ram breed - the control group (30 heads) - were on the main feed of the peasant farm and the experimental group of animals (70 heads) on the main feed together took feed additives 1 (FA1) granules for 60 days. The composition of FA1 included chlorella, bentonite, vitamins and minerals. The animals were selected by age and live weight. Live weight changes were determined by weighing the sheep individually every 15 days in the morning before feeding. The conditions of keeping and the general level of feeding of all experimental animals were similar. Animals of all groups were fed with specialized feed FA1; the average daily consumption of compound feed with a feed additive for fattening was 2880–2880 g, balanced in accordance with a detailed system of standardized feeding.

Improving the technology of growing young sheep is possible due to the improvement of conditions of maintenance and organization of full feeding. Creation of a complex biologically active additive based on natural components based on liquid chlorella and bentonite in a ratio of 1:3, which additionally contains active substances enriched with vitamins and minerals.

Chlorella is a microalgae known for its rich nutritional composition, including proteins, vitamins, minerals and antioxidants. Chlorella is valued for its complex composition and is used as a dietary supplement to support health, improve immunity and detoxify the body. Its composition may vary slightly depending on growing conditions, but the main components and elements are as follows:

Macronutrients: Proteins - about 50-60% of dry mass. Chlorella contains all essential amino acids. Carbohydrates - about 10-20% of dry mass, including complex carbohydrates and fiber. Fats - about 10-15% of dry mass. Among them are many polyunsaturated fatty acids, such as omega-3 and omega-6.

Vitamins: Vitamin C, B vitamins - including B1 (thiamine), B2 (riboflavin), B3 (niacin), B5 (pantothenic acid), B6, B9 (folic acid) and B12 (cobalamin). Vitamin E - an important antioxidant. Vitamin K (phyloquinone) - an antihemorrhagic vitamin.

Minerals and trace elements: Calcium (Ca), iron (Fe), iodine (I), magnesium (Mg), zinc (Zn), potassium (K), phosphorus (P), copper (Cu), selenium (Se), manganese (Mn), chromium (Cr).

Bentonite is natural clay rock rich in minerals and macro- and microelements. Its chemical composition may vary depending on the deposit, but the main components and elements are usually the following macronutrients: silicon (Si) - about 45-65%, aluminum (Al) - about 10-20%, iron (Fe) - about 1-6%, magnesium (Mg) - about 1-5%, calcium (Ca) - about 0.5-5%, sodium (Na) - about 0.5-5%, potassium (K) - about 0.5-3%. Microelements: Copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co), chromium (Cr), molybdenum (Mo), selenium (Se), lithium (Li), lead (Pb) - in trace amounts, cadmium (Cd) - in trace amounts, titanium (Ti) - in the form of titanium oxide (TiO_2), about 0.5–1%.

The content of vitamins and minerals in the composition of the feed additive in 100 g: vitamins - β -carotene - 5.83 mg, B1 -1.2 mg, B2 -0.8 mg, PP -2.39 mg, C -45.3 mg, E -8.2 mg. Minerals: calcium - 790 mg, iron - 3.34 mg, iodine - 425.29 mcg, copper - 2.79 mg, zinc - 7.13 mg. After feeding KD1, the animals were weighed and taken for the experiment to determine the physiological, biochemical and hematological parameters.

Table 1. Live weight of sheep.

Group of animals	«Mamed-Khasenov» PF, Hampshire, live weight, kg (n=50)		"Razakhun" PF, Kazakh meat and wool, live weight, kg (n=50)	
	Control (n=15)	Experimental (n=35)	Control (n=15)	Experimental (n=35)
Ewes	$65,0 \pm 0,28$	$65,6 \pm 0,70$	$52,0 \pm 0,17$	$52,7 \pm 0,32$

2.3. Physiological, biochemical and hematological studies

Physiological indices of animal growth were assessed: weight gain by weighing the sheep individually every 15 days in the morning before feeding and watering. Absolute, average daily and relative gains in live weight of rams were determined. Results of laboratory studies of biological material samples (blood, etc.) obtained from animals of various species delivered from different farms in the country's regions. For the study, blood was collected in vacuum tubes before morning feeding from the jugular vein at the time before and after the experiment: on the 1st day and on the 60th day of the experiment.

Peripheral blood samples (serum) were collected by centrifugation for 20 min/1000 rpm. The main biochemical parameters were determined in the blood samples: total protein level by the biuret method, protein fractions (albumin, α -, β -, γ -globulins) by the nephelometric method. The amount of α -amylase was determined by the amyloclastic method, the activity of lipase and trypsin was determined by the generally accepted methodology, creatinine - photometric method with picric acid - according to the Jaffe color reaction, urea - a systematic method using a solution of the color reaction of diacetylmonooxymone, alkaline phosphatase - according to the Lowry method, thymol test - according to the thymol-veronal buffer, the level of enzyme activity: alanine aminotransferase (AlAT), aspartate aminotransferase (AsAT) - according to the Reitman-Frenkel method, bilirubin - according to the Iendrasik-Hoff method, cholesterol, triglycerides, total lipids were determined by generally accepted methods using a set of reagents from the Bio-Lachema-Test company (Czech Republic), their indicators were determined using an automatic biochemical analyzer "COBOS INTEGRA 400" (USA) [Abdreshov, et al., 2015]. Glucose levels were determined using the Glucotpend-2 test strip with a standard test system, according to the attached instructions, with subsequent processing of the results obtained on the SOBOSINTEGRA 400 analyzer (USA). The cellular composition and physicochemical parameters of the blood, as well as its morphological composition, were studied on the SYSMEX KX-219 hematology analyzer (Japan).

2.4. Measurement of osmotic resistance of erythrocytes

The influence of feed additives on the blood cells of animals, were conducted research to determine the osmotic resistance of erythrocytes. Osmotic resistance of erythrocytes determination of optical density of hemoglobin solutions, obtained as a result of destruction of erythrocytes in a series of hypotonic solutions of sodium chloride, allowing obtaining curves of dynamics of hemolysis by the method [Waugh, et al., 1938; Penha-Silva, et al., 2007]. By cell resistance to hypotonic sodium chloride solutions. 25 μ l of erythrocytes were added to a series of test tubes containing 2.5 ml of solutions with different NaCl concentrations (0.85; 0.75; 0.65; 0.55; 0.50; 0.45; 0.35; 0.15; 0.1), thoroughly mixed and the samples were incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes. Hemolysis was stopped by adding an equal volume of solutions of the corresponding sodium chloride concentrations necessary to restore is tonicity. After centrifugation for 5 min at 2000 rpm, measurements were taken in the samples on a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 540 nm, and the percentage of hemolysis was calculated according to the formula [Walski, et al., 2014; Salvagno, et al., 2020], taking as 100% hemolysis in a sample containing a 0.1% sodium chloride solution. For quantitative assessment of osmotic resistance of erythrocytes, the osmoticity value corresponding to hemolysis of 50% of cells (C50) was used – the center of distribution of erythrocytes by osmotic resistance.

2.5. Analysis determination of lipid peroxidation

The intensity of LPO processes in erythrocyte membranes was assessed by the content of its products – diene conjugates (DC), malondialdehyde (MDA), catalase and superoxide dismutase activity, in accordance with generally accepted laboratory research methods [Behn, et al., 2007; Igbokwe, et al., 2016a; Li, et al., 2007]. The optical density of the supernatant liquid was measured at a wavelength of 532 nm against distilled water. At high temperatures in an acidic medium, malondialdehyde reacts with 2-thiobarbituric acid, forming a colored trimethine complex, with an absorption maximum at 52 nm. The content of thiobarbituric acid – active products (TBA-AP) of LPO – was determined by the fluorometric method [Wasowicz, et al., 1994; Jo, et al., 1998].

2.6. Statistical analysis

The experimental results were processed by the method of variation statistics on a computer (Microsoft Corporation, Washington, DC, USA) using Student's t-test. The mean \pm standard deviation (SD) was calculated and expressed as a percentage. Significance testing was performed using Fisher's t-test and Student's t-test to evaluate differences in mean values. The results were considered significant at $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of feed additive on sheep body weight

After 60 days of feeding the animals with FA1, the weight increased by 11.14-12.9% (72.91 ± 0.82 and 59.5 ± 0.64), in the control group by 2.1% (66.4 ± 0.71 and 53.09 ± 0.48). One of the main criteria characterizing the adaptation process is the dynamics of the animal's live weight, since it reflects the transition from the catabolic phase to the anabolic direction of metabolism, and also allows us to judge the general condition of the body. For animals after feeding the new feed additive for 60 days, a significant intensity of growth and development of the body was characteristic, that is, a rapid increase in body weight and body size and individual organs, improvement of all body systems compared to the control group of animals. By the end of the experiment, the live weight of the Hampshire breed (7.31 ± 0.2 kg), Kazakh meat wool (6.80 ± 0.7 kg) was higher than that of the control groups by 11.14-12.9% ($p < 0.05$). The average daily live weight gain of rams was 0.122 ± 0.0007 and 0.113 ± 0.004 kg ($p < 0.01$) and was also higher by 1.3 and 1.5% ($p < 0.05$), respectively, than that of the animals of the control group (Table 2).

Table 2. Live weight and average daily gain data for sheep in the control and experimental groups before and after feeding FA1.

Sheep breeding indicators	Hampshire (n=50)			Kazakh meat wool (n=50)		
	Control (n=15)	Experimental group FA1 (n=35)		Control (n=15)	Experimental group FA1 (n=35)	
		Day1	60days		Day1	60days
Total weight of animals, kg	$65,0 \pm 0,28$	$65,6 \pm 0,70$	$72,91 \pm 0,82$	$52,0 \pm 0,17$	$52,7 \pm 0,32$	$59,5 \pm 0,64$
Live weight gain, kg			$7,31 \pm 0,2$			$6,80 \pm 0,7$
Average daily increase in body weight, kg	$0,047 \pm 0,0009$	-	$0,122 \pm 0,0007$	$0,036 \pm 0,0005$	-	$0,113 \pm 0,004$

* - $p < 0.001$ between the control and the experimental group

The results of average daily gains are shown in Figure 1. Hampshire ewes had an average live weight of 65.6 ± 0.70 kg, Kazakh meat wool ewes 52.7 ± 0.32 kg. Later, with the increase in the age of both types of animal groups, after the use of the feed additive, the differences in their live weight changed over 15 days. In Hampshire breeds, after 15 days, the daily gains were 1.9 ± 0.014 kg, and in Kazakh meat wool ewes it was 2.5 ± 0.020 kg. Over the 30-day period, these figures were higher and amounted to 4.4 ± 0.015 kg and 4.1 ± 0.009 kg, respectively, by breed.

Higher weight gains in the experimental Hampshire breeds were observed starting from the 45th day of feeding, their average daily gains were 5.6 ± 0.038 kg. In the Kazakh meat wool breed, the weight indicators were 5.0 ± 0.011 kg. From the 60th day of feeding the feed additive, the maximum average daily gains were noted and were in the Hampshire breed 7.3 ± 0.021 kg. In the Kazakh meat wool breed 6.8 ± 0.014 kg. The effect of the FA1 on live weight in both groups of animals was 7.31 ± 0.2 kg and 6.80 ± 0.7 kg at the end of the experiment. Between the Hampshire and Kazakh meat wool breeds, these differences were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

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Figure 1. Dynamics of average daily live weight gains in both breeds of ewes (kilograms)

In particular, in ewes, in the diet of feeding a new feed additive 1, rich in vitamins and easily digestible nutrients, which contributed to an increase in their fatness and provided a higher live weight - 4.9 ± 0.19 kg. The live weight of the ewe was 8.2% lower. At the same time, the body of ewes inevitably loses energy when exposed to low temperatures, which affects the development of spring. One of the main criteria characterizing the adaptation process is the dynamics of the animal's live weight, since it reflects the transition from the catabolic phase to the anabolic direction of metabolism, and also allows us to judge the general condition of the body. In animals of both breeds after feeding the feed additive for 60 days, a significant growth rate, rapid increase in body weight and development of all body systems were shown. By the end of the first 60 days, the live weight of the Hampshire breed (10.7 ± 0.37 kg) was higher than that of the Kazakh meat wool breed by 4.6% ($p < 0.05$). The average daily and absolute gains in live weight in the Hampshire and Kazakh meat wool breeds were 193 g and 5.8 kg ($p < 0.01$) and were also higher by 1.5 and 1.7% ($p < 0.05$), respectively, than in the controls of both groups.

3.2. Biochemical and hematological parameters of sheep when feeding a feed additive

When comparing the control data with the parameters of the experimental group taking FA1, it was revealed in the blood that the analysis of the obtained data indicates fluctuations in the activity of transamination enzymes when feeding animals with the feed additive (Table 3).

Table 3. Biochemical parameters of blood plasma and lymph after the use of FA1.

Indicators	Hampshire		Kazakh meat wool	
	Control	FA1 – 60 days	Control	FA1 – 60 days
Total protein, g/l	72.81 ± 4.31	$80.43 \pm 2.11^*$	74.27 ± 4.89	$84.10 \pm 5.12^*$
Albumin, g/l	35.2 ± 1.8	38.4 ± 1.2	39.9 ± 1.6	42.6 ± 0.07
Globulins, g/l	32.2 ± 2.2	33.7 ± 2.8	34.1 ± 1.9	34.8 ± 2.5
α -globulins	8.2 ± 0.27	10.9 ± 0.16	9.1 ± 0.16	11.2 ± 0.27
β -globulins	10.1 ± 0.16	12.5 ± 0.16	10.7 ± 0.27	11.9 ± 0.27
γ -globulins	13.8 ± 0.27	15.2 ± 0.27	12.4 ± 0.16	14.8 ± 0.16
Total Amylase, U/L	12.8 ± 0.38	$20.39 \pm 3.1^{**}$	13.9 ± 0.07	$21.62 \pm 3.1^{**}$
Lipase, U/L	52.6 ± 3.38	$72.6 \pm 6.38^{**}$	54.2 ± 3.38	$78.4 \pm 5.17^{**}$
Trypsin, U/L	122 ± 7.4	138 ± 5.6	120 ± 4.9	137 ± 8.1
Glucose, g/l	3.55 ± 1.1	$4.12 \pm 0.24^*$	3.14 ± 0.03	$3.91 \pm 0.29^*$
HDL Cholesterol, mmol/L	2.67 ± 0.02	$2.48 \pm 0.01^*$	2.90 ± 0.04	$2.69 \pm 0.06^*$

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LDLCholesterol, mmol/L	0.71 ± 0.04	0.80 ± 0.07	0.72 ± 0.02	0.83 ± 0.08
Bilirubin, mkmol/L	3.30 ± 0.7	4.04 ± 0.12	3.7 ± 0.15	3.41 ± 0.09
Triglycerides, mmol/L	0.84 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.07**	0.89 ± 0.08	1.11 ± 0.01**
AlAT, mmol/L	89.70 ± 4.9	96.85 ± 5.15	103.8 ± 0.09	112.94 ± 7.79
AsAT, mmol/L	118.4 ± 9.3**	148.2 ± 9.23**	120.6 ± 0.16	148.26 ± 9.23**
Alkalinephosphatase, U/L	264.2 ± 10.4	301.7 ± 9.28*	255.5 ± 10.9	297.2 ± 8.36*
Urea, mmol/L	7.25 ± 0.52	4.47 ± 0.02*	7.81 ± 0.06	4.93 ± 0.49*
Creatinine, mmol/L	103.74 ± 5.9	95.89 ± 6.7	104.9 ± 4.8	96.90 ± 8.1
Notes: Reliable in comparison with the control group, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01				

During the research we have established that the concentration of proteins in Hampshire and Kazakh meat wool sheep breeds during feeding the feed additive undergoes significant changes and biochemical and hematological blood indices depend on the time of the season. In many ways, it depends on the level of feeding of ewes affects the development of live weight of animals, that it plays an important role in the health of the animal's body.

At the same time, the activity of AsAT during the period of feeding with the feed additive in Hampshire sheep increased by 0.11 mmol/l (7.9%), Kazakh meat wool - by 0.08 mmol/l (6.0%). The increase in AlAT activity in the analyzed feeding period was less significant and amounted to 0.05 mmol/h l (7.8%) and 0.04 mmol/l (6.9%), respectively, compared to the control group in the Hampshire and Kazakh meat wool breeds. The increase in the level of total protein in the blood of Hampshire and Kazakh meat wool sheep during feeding with the new feed additive by 4.8 (p < 0.05) and 2.3% (p < 0.05), albumins, α -, β -globulins - by 5.4; 15.9 (p < 0.01); 21.2% (p < 0.05) and 6.9; 20.0 (p < 0.01); 21.3% (p < 0.05), respectively, characterizes the protein-forming function of the liver and is an integral indicator of animal growth and development. A characteristic feature of the protein composition of the blood of the Hampshire breed is a higher level of globulins by 3.0% due to the β - and γ -globulin fraction by 6.2 and 10.6% (p < 0.05) compared to the Kazakh meat wool breed, which reflects the state of one of the forms of reactivity of the body, in particular, the synthesis of specific antibodies during the period of low temperatures.

This can explain the increase in the amount of β -globulin fraction in the blood of sheep, since they participate in the transport and regulation of lipid metabolism, have a relatively high specificity and low capacity, bind sex hormones, thus regulating their biological activity. In addition, an increase in γ -globulins by 33.5 (p < 0.01) and 31.7% (p < 0.01) was noted in the blood of sheep of both breeds during the winter season, which indicates an increase in protective properties and the formation of the immune status of their body. Biochemical blood parameters in Hampshire and Kazakh meat wool sheep correspond to the winter season and metabolic shifts occur in the blood of animals, including from the side of protein metabolism indicators, aimed at maintaining homeostasis.

Evaluating the changes in the activity of the digestive enzyme amylase, lipase and trypsin and the accompanying biochemical parameters of the blood in ewes of both groups under conditions after feeding with FA1, it can be assumed that these digestive enzymes perform numerous vital functions in providing the catabolic component of protein and energy metabolism. The results of experiments with the addition of the feed additive in the amount of 100 mg / kg body weight showed that significant changes in the activity of digestive enzymes in the blood of ewes of both groups were not noted. After feeding with the feed additive, the content of amylase, lipase and trypsin in the blood of the Hampshire breed was increased by 59%, 38%, 13%, and in the Kazakh meat wool breed, the values of these indicators were 55.5%, 45%, 14% in accordance with the control group (p ≤ 0.01). The level of trypsin activity in the blood of animals is associated with the secretory function of the pancreas and liver. This is consistent with an increase in the activity of alkaline phosphatase by 1.2 times, which indicates an increasing load on the liver. Lipid metabolism changes due to the intensive formation and entry of cholesterol into the blood. As for carbohydrate metabolism, the glucose level in the blood of all the animals studied was within the reference values. A reliable significant increase in the values of this indicator was noted in animals in the diet receiving new FA1. Carbohydrate metabolism also increases, since the blood glucose level increases by 16.5% and 25%, respectively, compared to the control group. Therefore, the use of FA 1 enhances

metabolism in the sheep's body, increasing the function of the digestive glands, digestibility and absorption of nutrients.

The dynamics of protein metabolism indicators in Hampshire and Kazakh meat wool sheep is due to structural and functional changes in the body during the winter period. In addition, this period of ontogenesis coincides with the onset of lactation in sheep, characterized by an increase in sex hormones in the blood. Vegetative and hormonal mechanisms for regulating adaptation processes to external influences are intensively formed in the sheep's body, which is accompanied by changes in the morphofunctional and physiological status of the body [Asres, et al., 2014; Berihulay, et al., 2019]. Protein metabolism indices in animals during the winter season reflect the development of growth and weight associated with some aspects of the body's immunobiological reactivity, which allows us to judge the metabolic adaptation and the possibility of further economic use of animals. In ewes of both breeds, a high concentration of total protein was noted 72.5 ± 1.6 and 70.0 ± 1.2 g/l, respectively, associated with its receipt with a new feed additive. The globulin fraction was predominant in the blood. The ewes of both breeds had a low albumin level of 35.2 ± 1.8 and 39.9 ± 1.6 g/l. Moreover, in the ewes of both groups, the albumin concentration was 9-6.9% higher ($p < 0.01$), respectively, and globulins differed insignificantly from the control groups. The amount of α -globulins in the blood serum of the Hampshire breed showed an increase of 32.9%, and in the Kazakh meat wool breed it was 23.1% ($p < 0.01$). The level of β -globulins in the blood serum was 23.7% and 11.2% ($p < 0.01$), respectively, higher than in the ewes of the control group of both breeds (Table 1). The study showed that the addition of a feed additive in both sheep breeds led to a significant increase in the number of leukocytes, erythrocytes and hemoglobin, while the fractions of globulin were slightly increased, however, no effect was observed for albumin and globulin [Guo, et al., 2019; Shedeed, et al., 2019].

At the same time, a significant increase in proteins that have a plastic value in the body was recorded in the blood of ewes of both groups. Albumins and α , β -globulins, which characterizes an increase in the intensity of metabolism, since α -globulins are metabolically highly active and easily attach carbohydrates, lipids, transport cholesterol and vitamins. Indicators of the levels of total protein and albumin in the blood plasma of sheep of both groups, characterizing the state of its transport systems that bind nutrients, vitamins, trace elements, hormones and other metabolic substances in plasma and deliver them to tissues, showed little change after feeding with a feed additive for 1-60 days. We consider this confirmation to be in the mechanisms of maintaining homeostasis, the possibility of animals adapting to the conditions of a particular environment.

It is known that cholesterol is one of the main structural and functional components of biological membranes, and also participates in the regulation of vascular tone and hemostasis reactions. It was shown that the level of LDL cholesterol significantly changed - increased by 12.6-15.3% - after feed additive 1 compared to the control in both breed groups and significantly increased by 1.1 and 1.2 times ($p < 0.05$). The indicators after feed additive 1 HDL cholesterol decreased in the Hampshire breed by 7.1 and in the Kazakh meat wool ewe breed by 7.2% - compared to the control ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3). It is generally recognized that the level of cholesterol, including LDL cholesterol obtained from the diet, and endogenous synthesis. In this regard, it can be concluded that the provision of feed immediately after the new diet ensures rapid renewal of body reserves.

Triglycerides are derivatives of glycerol and higher fatty acids that are obtained from food and are the main source of energy (15). The content of triglycerides in the blood serum increased significantly by 30% ($p \leq 0.01$) and by 24.7% ($p \leq 0.01$) compared to the control group.

Increased activity of blood enzymes may be a consequence of accelerated synthesis processes, decreased excretion rate, and increased permeability of cell membranes. It is known that the adaptability of animals to certain conditions can be judged by physiological and biochemical features, which to a certain extent can also characterize the productive qualities of animals. Studies by other authors have established a close relationship between the live weight of animals and its growth with the activity of serum transamination enzymes [Pappas, et al., 1988]. This is due to the fact that transaminases – AsAT and AlAT, carrying out the reversible process of transferring the amino group of amino acids to keto acids, essentially control the intensity and direction of protein metabolism in the body of animals.

Urea is the end product of protein metabolism in the body, its content in the control group in both groups of ewes was 7.25–7.81 mmol/l and corresponded to physiological norms, since it is mainly excreted

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by the kidneys. After feeding with FA1, these indicators in both groups decreased by 1.6 times compared to the control group of ewes. Determination of its content in the blood provides a rationale for the possibility of assessing the functional capabilities of the kidneys.

Creatinine is one of the important metabolites of protein metabolism, takes an active part in the energy metabolism of muscle and other tissues, and its content depends on the adequacy of feeding rations, especially the protein part, which ensures an increase in the average daily gain in live weight, including muscle mass of experimental animals [Abdreshov, et al., 2018]. Its content in the blood serum in our experiments was within 103.74-104.9 mmol/l, without significant differences between the groups, and corresponded to the standard indicators.

The use of FA1 showed the advantage of their use - high caloric content (glucose) and its protein saturation against the background of a slight increase in the level of cholesterol and low-density lipids utilized in the liver. Triglycerides show mainly the activity of protein-carbohydrate metabolism, promoting muscle mass growth without damage to hepatocytes. The revealed changes in biochemical activity in the blood of the experimental group of both groups taking FA1 are closer to the control data and the physiological norm, while the enzyme indicators AlAT, AsAT, bilirubin in the group of animals taking FA1 were higher than normal, which shows a tendency to enhance the work of the hepatobiliary system, an increase in cytolytic activity. Based on the results of biochemical studies, it can be stated that not only the parameters of the gastrointestinal tract, but also the parameters of the blood are subject to change. The increased levels of amylase, lipase, and alkaline phosphatase are explained by the activity of this enzyme and its appearance in the bloodstream and, in general, in the circulatory system of the body, and this, in turn, indicates the rapid onset of the feed additive in the gastrointestinal tract [Nanji, et al., 1989; Abdreshov, et al., 2019]. The study showed that the activity of enzymes involved in protein metabolism, the most pronounced changes were observed in the activity of AlAT in all studied animals - above the upper limit of the norm. In addition, a change in AsAT activity was observed in both groups of sheep receiving the new feed additive. Since the FA1 contains trace elements, antioxidants and other biologically active substances, it can be assumed that the increase in the activity of AlAT and AsAT is associated with the continuous intake of minerals included in these FA1.

The results of the clinical blood test of the sheep under study are shown in Table 4. Thus, in the blood of animals of the control group on the 60th day after the feed additive, a slight increase in the level of erythrocytes to $4.7 \pm 1.3 \cdot 10^{12}/l$ was observed compared to the lower limit of the norm. In animals of all groups, an increase in the hemoglobin level was noted during the experiment. A tendency towards a decrease in the level of platelets was noted in the ewe of both groups; in the Hampshire and Kazakh meat wool breeds after the use of the feed additive after 60 days it was $221 \pm 15.4 \cdot 10^9/l$. The leukocyte formula was recorded in all animals under study compared to the reference values.

An increase in the level of eosinophils was noted in the blood of animals of all studied groups in the Hampshire breed by 13.5% and in the Kazakh meat wool breed by 18.6% before feeding, these indicators were respectively ($3.12 \pm 0.3\%$ and $2.74 \pm 0.92\%$). The most pronounced increase in the percentage of basophils was noted in the blood of animals of the control of both groups ($0.35 \pm 0.03\%$ and $0.32 \pm 0.07\%$) and the period of feeding the feed additive in the blood of animals it was ($0.47 \pm 0.04\%$ and $0.43 \pm 0.09\%$). After feeding the ewes for 60 days, a statistically significant difference of 34.3% of basophils was noted in the blood of both groups, respectively (Table 4).

In sheep of both blood groups, when feeding the feed additive, the erythrocyte membrane undergoes destructive changes, a decrease in the osmotic resistance of erythrocytes and a change in the activation of LPO processes are observed. Measuring the osmotic resistance of erythrocytes is an important research method not only in vitro experiments, but also a diagnostic method in medicine and is used to study the mechanism of pathological processes and the action of some drugs and biologically active compounds.

Table 4. Cellular composition of the blood of sheep in the experimental group when feeding them FA-1 for 60 days.

Indicators	Hampshire		Kazakh meat wool	
	Control	FA1 – 60 days	Control	FA1 – 60 days
Leucocyte, $10^9/l$	9.69 ± 0.47	9.93 ± 0.35	9.79 ± 0.58	9.84 ± 0.58

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Erythrocyte, $10^{12}/\text{л}$	12.34 ± 0.21	12.78 ± 0.78	12.35 ± 0.29	12.91 ± 0.23
Hemoglobin, г/л	106.9 ± 3.78	110.0 ± 2.36	111.2 ± 4.61	115.45 ± 5.91
Hematocrit, %	42.23 ± 0.47	44.56 ± 1.94	42.67 ± 0.85	45.89 ± 1.94
Platelets, $10^9/\text{л}$	405.4 ± 14.4	$509.5 \pm 26^{**}$	421.6 ± 21.5	$578.9 \pm 23.7^{**}$
Leukocyte formula				
Eosinophils, %	3.12 ± 0.3	3.34 ± 0.3	2.25 ± 0.80	3.25 ± 0.80
Neutrophils, %	56.1 ± 2.5	58.4 ± 1.9	58.82 ± 6.08	59.82 ± 4.00
Lymphocytes, %	39.73 ± 3.11	43.16 ± 3.72	45.17 ± 10.24	46.9 ± 3.65
Monocytes, %	2.9 ± 0.01	2.4 ± 0.05	2.68 ± 0.04	2.91 ± 0.07
Basophils, %	0.35 ± 0.03	$0.47 \pm 0.04^{**}$	0.32 ± 0.07	$0.43 \pm 0.09^{**}$
Notes: Reliable in comparison with the control group, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$				

During the experiments, hematological indices of animal blood were studied. The results of the studies are presented in Table 4. Hematocrit indices for the entire period of the experiment were within the physiological norms (35-45%) and no reliable changes were observed. The average value was: in both control groups - 42.48% and 42.67%, and ewes of the experimental groups had 44.56% and 45.89%, respectively. The number of platelets at the beginning of the experiment in the blood of animals of the control groups was within the physiological norms ($250-450 \times 10^9/\text{l}$), and the indices in both experimental groups after feeding with the feed additive were higher by 26% and 37.3%, respectively. At the end of the experiment, all indices were and corresponded to higher values of the physiological norm, and no reliable changes were observed.

During the entire period of the experiment, the concentration of leukocytes in the control and experimental groups were within the physiological norms and had an average value of $9.69 \times 10^9/\text{l}$ for the Hampshire breed and $9.84 \times 10^9/\text{l}$ for the Kazakh meat wool breed - the control group, in the experiment after the feed additive in both groups of ewes did not change compared to the control group. The content of lymphocytes and neutrophils at the beginning and end of the experiment in the control and experimental groups was within the physiological norms and did not have reliable changes. The ratio of basophils at the beginning of the experiment was within the physiological norms and at the end of the experiment tended to increase by 34% in both groups of ewes. All indicators did not go beyond the physiological norms, and reliable changes were not observed.

Thus, according to the results of the experiment, the use of a new FA1 on the biochemical parameters of blood has established the most positive effect of these complexes on the indicators of protein and carbohydrate metabolism of sheep of both groups during the feeding period. The uses of new feed additives show the benefits of farming and occupy a central place in the science of animal nutrition used as animal feed additives. In addition, it has been proven that new feed additives have a positive effect on productivity, digestibility, animal growth, immunity and antioxidant status. To solve these problems, further research is needed to clarify the mechanisms of action of various plant feed additives and their practical application in the nutrition of ruminants.

3.3. Results of hemolysis of red blood cells and analysis determination of lipid peroxidation

Using data on the osmotic resistance of erythrocytes, it is possible to assess their physicochemical properties of blood to various effects, since the osmotic resistance of erythrocytes reflects the stability of cell membranes. As a result of our research, specific features of osmotic resistance of erythrocytes were found in the experiment on the animal organism. Table 5 presents data on the state of osmotic resistance of erythrocytes in various concentrations of sodium chloride solution in animals of all observation groups. In the control ewe of both groups, the onset point of hemolysis corresponded to 0.55% sodium chloride solution, lysis of erythrocytes exceeded 12.13%. More than half (61.5%) of lysed erythrocytes were detected in 0.45% sodium chloride solution. The onset of maximum hemolysis was observed in 0.40% sodium chloride solution (83%). Maximum (94.6%) hemolysis corresponded to a solution concentration of 0.2% (Table 5).

Table 5. Indicators of osmotic resistance of erythrocytes in various concentrations of sodium chloride solution in animals of control and experimental groups are shown, %.

Concentration of NaCl solution	Relative content of lysed erythrocytes in the blood. %		
	Control animals	Hampshire	Kazakh meat wool
0.85	3.29 ± 0.06	4.98 ± 0.72	4.46 ± 0.34
0.75	4.56 ± 0.61	5.96 ± 0.21	5.82 ± 0.11
0.65	4.97 ± 0.49	8.76 ± 0.51**	7.89 ± 0.55**
0.55	11.47 ± 0.36	17.78 ± 1.12**	17.96 ± 0.49**
0.50	27.93 ± 1.56	36.09 ± 1.53*	37.85 ± 1.62*
0.45	58.12 ± 1.36	72.51 ± 1.08**	73.04 ± 1.83**
0.35	82.95 ± 1.88	86.23 ± 1.37	84.23 ± 1.28
0.15	94.56 ± 1.19	96.672 ± 0.61	95.09 ± 1.86

After 60 days of feeding with the feed additive, the osmotic resistance of erythrocytes of the onset of hemolysis in the Hampshire breed shifted towards a higher concentration of sodium chloride solution - 0.65% (the percentage of hemolysis corresponded to 8.76, $p < 0.05$). In a 0.55% sodium chloride solution, the percentage of hemolyzed erythrocytes increased by 55% ($p < 0.05$) compared to the intact group (Table 5). At the point of 50% hemolysis, the number of hemolyzed erythrocytes increased compared to the norm by 29.2% ($p < 0.05$) and significantly approached the point of maximum hemolysis (70%). This indicates a decrease in the zone of maximum resistance. It can be noted that at points of sodium chloride solution concentration from 0.65% to 0.45%, the percentage of hemolysis exceeded the indicators of the control group ($p < 0.05$ at all points).

After 60 days of feeding the feed additive in the Kazakh meat wool breed, similar results were observed (Table 5). At the point of minimal resistance (0.55% solution), the percentage of hemolyzed erythrocytes was lower than in the control group by 56.6% ($p < 0.05$). In sodium chloride solutions with concentrations of 0.50%, 0.45% and 0.40%, a significant decrease in the percentage of hemolyzed erythrocytes was noted compared to the control group of ewes. In subsequent more hypotonic concentrations of sodium chloride solution, the indicators in all observation groups did not differ significantly. It is shown that feeding animals with the feed additive for 60 days reveals common mechanisms that are expressed in more stable parameters of osmotic resistance of erythrocytes.

The activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) was significantly higher in ewes of both groups of animals by 29.8 and 31.6%, respectively, compared to the control group. The data obtained show that SOD plays a key role in the body, since an increase in SOD in the blood with a feed additive reduces oxidative stress and improves the antioxidant defense of the body. The identified changes in the antioxidant defense system indicate that the processes are aimed at maintaining the necessary balance characteristic of physiological metabolic reactions of the body. Thus, in comparison with the control group, a reliable decrease in the level of malondialdehyde 18.6% and 16.1% was found in both breeds of sheep compared to the control group. Studies have shown an increase in diene conjugates in erythrocyte membranes in both the Hampshire breed and the Kazakh meat wool breed by 23.3% -27.9%, respectively (Table 6).

Table 6. Changes in indicators of lipid peroxidation and antioxidant activity in the membranes of erythrocytes inbreeds sheep of the Hampshire and Kazakh meat wool after a feed additive.

Animals group	Indicators		
	Superoxide dismutase (SOD), units/mL of red blood cells	Diene conjugates (DC), nmol/ml	MДА, nmol/ml
Hampshire			
Control	1.99 ± 0.03	2.44 ± 0.03	0.131 ± 0.01
Experimental group	2.59 ± 0.07**	3.01 ± 0.05*	0.111 ± 0.07**
Kazakh meat wool			
Control	2.17 ± 0.08	2.47 ± 0.09	0.139 ± 0.04
Experimental group	2.86 ± 0.050**	3.17 ± 0.02*	0.119 ± 0.06**

Notes: Reliable in comparison with the control group, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

Experiments have shown that after the application of feed additive 1, the antioxidant properties of red blood cells were reduced, malondialdehyde was reduced, and SOD was increased. Other researchers point out that antioxidant compounds suppress the body's oxidative reactions [Muñoz-Cuautle, et al., 2022; Piao, et al., 2023]. Thus, the analysis of the mechanisms of cellular homeostasis in sheep blood under the conditions of feeding a new feed additive shows that they are extremely complex. Feed additives lead to minor changes in homeostasis in animals, characterized by significant activation of lipid peroxidation processes. The revealed changes in the antioxidant defense system indicate that the processes are aimed at maintaining the necessary balance characteristic of the physiological metabolic reactions of the body. The activity of SOD is usually sufficient to inactivate reactive oxygen species at the site of their formation, preventing the diffusion of tissue macromolecules into the environment. A change in the permeability of membranes for electrolytes when feeding sheep with a new feed additive leads to their redistribution between extracellular and intracellular spaces, which normalize the acid-base balance of the blood and water-electrolyte metabolism in the body.

4. Conclusions

The use of the feed additive in the diet of ewes of both groups has a positive effect on their health and productivity. Analysis of the results showed that the use of the new FA1 was the most effective in the experimental group, which was reflected in the corresponding changes in the biochemical and hematological composition of the blood, as well as the physiological status. Metabolic indices (protein, carbohydrate and other metabolism) in the blood of Hampshire and Kazakh meat wool sheep change during the feeding period in connection with their age, in accordance with the structural and functional reorganizations of the body, caused by genetic factors, and depend on the seasonal factor accompanying it (natural and climatic conditions, type of feeding of ewes, etc.). The use of new FA1 play a major role in metabolism, they are regulators of the normal state of the body, serve as a transport for the transfer of vitamins, minerals.

Declarations

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Author's Contributions: Conceptualization, SNA; data curation: AYE and GAD; formal analysis, SNA and MAY; methodology, LUK, UKN and AMK, project administration, YKM; resources, MAY, AYE, UKN and EYM; supervision, GAD and YKM; visualization, AMK and EEM; writing – original draft: SNA, writing – review & editing, SNA, GAD and MAY. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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